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GERRETSEN TENGSIZLIGI VA UNING TADBIQLARIGA DOIR BA'ZI MASALALAR TAHLILI

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu ishda Gerretsen teoremasi qaralgan. Ularga doir o'quvchilar hamda talabalar o'rtasida bo'lib o'tadigan fan olimpiadalaridagi ba'zi masalalar yechimlari tahlil qilingan. Mustaqil ishlash uchun masalalar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar. Gerretsen teoremasi, uchburchak, uchburchakka ichki va tashqi chizilgan aylana radiusi, yarim perimetr.

So'nggi yillarda geometriyada tengsizliklar usullari alohida o'rin egallab, olimpiada va oliy ta'lim kurslarida eng samarali vositalardan biriga aylandi. Uchburchak va ko'pburchaklarga doir tengsizliklarni yechishda ko'pincha bitta formulani emas, balki ketma-ket qo'llanadigan umumiy usullarni bilish hal qiluvchi ahamiyatga ega. Bu o'rinda keng qo'llaniladigan tengsizliklardan biri Gerretsen tengsizligidir. Gerretsen tengsizligi uchburchakning unga ichki va tashqi chizilgan aylana radiusi hamda yarim perimetri orasidagi bog'lanishni ifodalaydi.

Teorema. Ixtiyoriy $\triangle ABC$ uchburchak uchun quyidagi tengsizlik bajariladi:

(Bu yerda R -tashqi chizilgan aylana radiusi, r - ichki chizilgan aylana radiusi, $s = \frac{a+b+c}{2}$)

$$16Rr - 5r^2 \leq s^2 \leq 4R^2 + 4Rr + 3r^2$$

1-misol. Ixtiyoriy $\triangle ABC$ uchburchak uchun quyidagi tengsizlikni isbotlang:

$$s^2 \leq 4R^2 + 8Rr$$

Yechimi: Gerretsen teoremasiga ko'ra: $16Rr - 5r^2 \leq s^2 \leq 4R^2 + 4Rr + 3r^2$

Bizga kerak bo'lgan maqsad: $s^2 \leq 4R^2 + 8Rr$

$$4R^2 + 4Rr + 3r^2 \leq 4R^2 + 8Rr \quad 3r^2 \leq 4Rr \quad r \leq \frac{4}{3}R$$

Uchburchak uchun Euler tengsizligiga ko'ra $R \geq 2r$ dan $r \leq \frac{R}{2} < \frac{4}{3}R$

Gerretson tengsizligidan

$$s^2 \leq 4R^2 + 4Rr + 3r^2 \leq 4R^2 + 8Rr \quad s^2 \leq 4R^2 + 8Rr$$

2-misol. Ixtiyoriy $\triangle ABC$ uchburchak uchun quyidagi tengsizlikni isbotlang:

$$R^2 - Rr + r^2 \geq \frac{s^2}{12}$$

Yechim: $16Rr - 5r^2 \leq s^2 \leq 4R^2 + 4Rr + 3r^2$ (Gerretson teoremasi)

$$s^2 \leq 12(R^2 - Rr + r^2)$$

Ikki tenglikni o'ng tomonini taqqoslasak:

$$12(R^2 - Rr + r^2) - (4R^2 + 4Rr + 3r^2) = 8R^2 - 16Rr + 9r^2$$

$$8R^2 - 16Rr + 9r^2 = 8(R - r)^2 + r^2 \geq 0$$

$$4R^2 + 4Rr + 3r^2 \leq 12(R^2 - Rr + r^2)$$

$$s^2 \leq 4R^2 + 4Rr + 3r^2 \leq 12(R^2 - Rr + r^2)$$

$$s^2 \leq 12(R^2 - Rr + r^2) \quad \rightarrow \quad R^2 - Rr + r^2 \geq \frac{s^2}{12}$$

3-misol. Uchburchak ABC uchun

$(ab + bc + ca)(s^2 + r^2) \geq 4abc(s + 3r)$ ni isbotlang.

Yechim: Bizga malumki, $ab + bc + ca = s^2 + r^2 + 4Rr$ va $abc = 4Rrs$

Bundan $(s^2 + r^2 + 4Rr)(s^2 + r^2) \geq 16Rrs^2 + 36R^2r^2$

Chap tarafni $X = s^2 + r^2$ deb belgilab ochamiz:

$$X(X + 4Rr) = X^2 + 4RrX$$

$$s^4 + 2s^2r^2 + r^4 + 4Rrs^2 + 4Rr^3 \geq 16Rrs^2 + 36R^2r^2$$

Hamma narsani o'ng tomonga o'tkazib, s^2 -li hadlarni guruhlab yozsak:

$$s^4 + s^2(2r^2 - 12Rr) \geq 36R^2r^2 - 4Rr^3 - r^4$$

$$(s^2 - 6Rr + r^2)^2 = s^4 + s^2(2r^2 - 12Rr) + (6Rr - r^2)^2$$

$$(s^2 - 6Rr + r^2)^2 \geq (6Rr - r^2)^2 + 36R^2r^2 - 4Rr^3 - r^4$$

O'ng tomonni soddalashtirsak: $(6Rr - r^2)^2 + 36R^2r^2 - 4Rr^3 - r^4 = 72R^2r^2 - 16Rr^3$

Natijada $(s^2 - 6Rr + r^2)^2 \geq 72R^2r^2 - 16Rr^3$

Gerretsen tengsizligining quyi bahosi: $s^2 \geq 16Rr - 5r^2$

Shundan $s^2 - 6Rr + r^2 \geq (16Rr - 5r^2) - 6Rr + r^2 = 10Rr - 4r^2$

$$\text{ya'ni } (s^2 - 6Rr + r^2)^2 \geq (10Rr - 4r^2)^2$$

Shu bois yuqoridagi natijani tugatish uchun quyidagini tekshirish kifoya:

$$(10Rr - 4r^2)^2 \geq 72R^2r^2 - 16Rr^3 \Leftrightarrow (R - 2r)(7R - 2r) \geq 0$$

Eyler tengsizligiga ko'ra $R \geq 2r$ dan $(R - 2r)(7R - 2r) \geq 0$ kelib chiqdi, demak dastlabki tengsizlik to'liq isbotlandi.

$(ab + bc + ca)(s^2 + r^2) = 4abc(s + 3r)$ faqat teng tomonli uchburchakda yuz beradi.

4-misol. Uchburchak ABC uchun isbotlang (ichki markaz I, tashqi aylana radiusi R, ichki radius r)

$$\sqrt{12(R^2 - Rr + r^2)} \geq AI + BI + CI \geq 6r$$

Chap tomon. $AI^2 = bc - 4Rr$; $BI^2 = ca - 4Rr$; $CI^2 = ab - 4Rr$:

Koshi-Shvars tengsizligidan:

$$3(AI^2 + BI^2 + CI^2) \geq (AI + BI + CI)^2 \Leftrightarrow \sqrt{3(s^2 + r^2 - 8Rr)} \geq AI + BI + CI$$

Endi quyidagini ko'rsatamiz: $\sqrt{3(s^2 + r^2 - 8Rr)} \leq \sqrt{12(R^2 - Rr + r^2)}$

bu esa ekvivalent: $s^2 + r^2 + 8Rr \leq 4R^2 - 4Rr + 4r^2 \Leftrightarrow s^2 \leq 4R^2 + 4Rr + 3r^2$

O'ng tomon. Ma'lumki:

$$AI = \frac{r}{\sin \frac{A}{2}} \quad BI = \frac{r}{\sin \frac{B}{2}} \quad CI = \frac{r}{\sin \frac{C}{2}}$$

$$6r \leq \frac{r}{\sin \frac{A}{2}} + \frac{r}{\sin \frac{B}{2}} + \frac{r}{\sin \frac{C}{2}}$$

ya'ni

$$2 \leq \frac{\frac{1}{\sin \frac{A}{2}} + \frac{1}{\sin \frac{B}{2}} + \frac{1}{\sin \frac{C}{2}}}{3}$$

$$\frac{\frac{1}{\sin \frac{A}{2}} + \frac{1}{\sin \frac{B}{2}} + \frac{1}{\sin \frac{C}{2}}}{3} \geq \csc \frac{A+B+C}{6}$$

$A + B + C = \pi$ bo'lganidan, $\csc(\pi/6) = 2$ va natija keladi:

$AI + BI + CI \geq 6r$.

5-misol. Ixtiyoriy ΔABC uchburchak uchun quyidagi tengsizlikni isbotlang:

$$\sum \frac{1}{2 - \cos A} \geq 2 \geq 3 \sum \frac{1}{5 - \cos A}$$

$$\sum \cos A = 1 + r/R, \quad \sum \cos A \cos B = (s^2 + r^2 - 4R^2)/(4R^2),$$

$$\prod \cos A = (s^2 - (2R + r)^2)/(4R^2)$$

Chap tomoni: $\sum 1/(2 - \cos A) \geq 2$

Eyler $2r \leq R$ va Gerretsen $s^2 \leq 4R^2 + 4Rr + 3r^2$ dan:

$$s^2 \leq 4R^2 + 8Rr - 5r^2$$

Identitetlar orqali quyidagiga teng kuchli:

$$4(1 + r/R) + 2 \cdot \frac{s^2 - (2R + r)^2}{4R^2} \geq 4 + 3 \cdot \frac{s^2 + r^2 - 4R^2}{4R^2} \rightarrow$$

$$4 \sum \cos A + 2 \prod \cos A \geq 4 + 3 \sum \cos A \cos B$$

$(2 - \cos A)$ bilan ekvivalent ko‘rinish:

$$\sum (2 - \cos A)(2 - \cos B) \geq 2 \cdot \prod (2 - \cos A)$$

Shundan: $\sum \frac{1}{2 - \cos A} \geq 2$ O‘ng tomoni: $3 \sum \frac{1}{5 - \cos A} \leq 2$

Eyler $2r \leq R$ va Gerretsen $16Rr - 5r^2 \leq s^2$ dan:

$$\frac{72Rr - 9r^2}{5} \leq s^2$$

$$20(1 + r/R) + 2 \cdot \frac{s^2 - (2R + r)^2}{4R^2} \leq 25 + 7 \cdot \frac{s^2 + r^2 - 4R^2}{4R^2} \rightarrow$$

$$20 \sum \cos A + 2 \prod \cos A \leq 25 + 7 \sum \cos A \cos B$$

$(5 - \cos A)$ bilan ekvivalent ko‘rinish:

$$\sum (5 - \cos A)(5 - \cos B) \leq \frac{2}{3} \cdot \prod (5 - \cos A)$$

Shundan:

$$\sum \frac{1}{5 - \cos A} \leq \frac{2}{3}$$

Mustaqil yechish uchun misollar:

1. Ixtiyoriy ΔABC uchburchak uchun quyidagi tengsizlikni isbotlang: $r(4R + r) \geq \sqrt{3}\Delta$

2. ABC uchburchak uchun ushbu tengsizlikni isbotlang: $\sqrt{\frac{15}{4} + \sum \cos A} - B \geq \sum \sin A$

3. ABC uchburchak uchun ushbu tengsizlikni isbotlang: $\sum \cos \frac{B - C^2}{2} \geq 24 \cdot \prod \sin \frac{A}{2}$

4. ΔABC uchburchak uchun $(\sum a b)(s^2 + r^2) \geq 4abc s + 36R^2 r^2$ ni isbotlang.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR RO‘YXATI: (REFERENCES)

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